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Autophagic regulation by NLRP7.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

NLR influence over autophagic function included regulation of Rubicon, ATG9B, ATG3 and ATG4A.